
Sharpening the trailing edge in the ILCA centerboard: investigation on a NACA Airfoil

Gianmario Broccia¹

¹ *Second Level Specializing Master in Aerospace System Engineering; M.Sc. in Energy Engineering graduated at the University of Cagliari – DIEE; Racing SailCoach for the Royal Yachting Association and the Italian Sailing Federation (FIV); ILCA6 Athlete.*

Reception date of the manuscript: dd/mm/yyyy

Acceptance date of the manuscript: dd/mm/yyyy

Publication date: dd/mm/yyyy

Abstract— The following paper wants to study the effect of sharpening the trailing edge of the new epoxy ILCA centerboard plunged in a water stream. The common experience always suggested that an open trailing edge would bring higher drag, especially when planing, resulting in a peculiar whistle. The goal is to shed the first light on the objective benefit of this practice.

Keywords— Hydrofoil; CFD; Comsol

I. INTRODUCTION

Sailing often relies on the subjective experience of the athlete concerning boat settings and best practices. In the ILCA [1] class (born “Laser Class” in 1971) one of those common practices has been sharpening the trailing edge of the centerboard by hand using a rasp, in the attempt of stopping a characteristic whistle owed to high-speed related vibrations. The idea behind it was to reduce the depression area right behind the flat trailing edge, where a vortex-shedding process can take place. This was especially considered in the case of the old foam centerboard, particularly bound to vibrate due to the flexibility of the edge, which was commonly referred to as the “humming-foil” phenomenon. This process represented a limit in the maximum speed as the vibrating trailing edge would increase the frontal area seen by the flow. Since 2010 the centerboard and the rudder were replaced by a new epoxy version with higher resistance to bending and hits. The study was achieved with a Comsol CFD simulation to assess Velocity and Pressure conditions within a given range of speeds and angles of attack. The aim was not to compute the total drag over the whole body of the centerboard, but rather exploit the results from a 2D profile and obtain a percentual difference for the drag values in different cases.

II. CENTERBOARD AND NACA AIRFOILS

The model is largely based on the built-in Comsol Example of the NACA 0012 Airfoil [2] which analyzes the flow around an inclined profile using the SST (Shear Stress Trans-

Fig. 1: Epoxy ILCA Centerboard

port) model developed by F.R. Menter in 1994 [3] and compares the results with the experimental lift data of Ladson [4] and pressure data of Gregory and O’Reilly [5]. The following paper will not report in detail a full description of the model since a thorough and better one can be found in the official Comsol manual, which reading is strongly recommended for a better comprehension of the following work. NACA airfoils are a series of wing-shaped profiles created by the former National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics [6] and generated using analytical equations that describe the camber (curvature) of the mean line concerning the horizontal chord line. In this case, the NACA profile chosen to represent the centerboard is a 4th series NACA profile where:

- the first digit indicates the maximum curvature as a percentage of the chord;
- the second digit gives the distance of the point of maximum curvature from the leading edge expressed as a

percentage of the chord and in multiples of 10;

- the last two digits describe the maximum thickness of the airfoil expressed as a percentage of the chord.

Thanks to the ILCA Class Rules Manual [7] the main dimensions of the centerboard are known, showing a horizontal chord of 370 mm with a maximum thickness of 33 mm, meaning a thickness-chord ratio equal to about 8.92%. In this sense, the NACA 0009 model would be the most suitable for the analysis. In reality, the generation of a NACA airfoil can be done directly within the geometry of Comsol by using the Parametric Curve function with the following analytic equation [8]:

$$y_t = 5T(a_0x^{0.5} + a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3 + a_4x^4) \quad (1)$$

where:

- y_t is the y value of a half thickness and needs to be applied on both sides of the camber line (done in Comsol with the Mirror function);
- the coefficients are $a_0 = 0.2969$, $a_1 = -0.126$, $a_2 = -0.3516$, $a_3 = 0.2843$, $a_4 = -0.1015$;
- T is the thickness-chord ratio.

It must be noted that the part of the equation within the brackets is referred to a 20% thick airfoil while the parameter $5T$ serves to adjust the final value to the correct thickness. Moreover, the last parameter a_4 can be turned to 0.1036 in case a closed trailing edge is desired. Tuning this last value, it is possible to obtain different thicknesses for the trailing edge of the centerboard which results to be 2 mm according to the measurements taken from a sample piece produced by Performance Sailing Australia (PSA). To have this precise value, a_4 is to be changed from 0.1015 to 0.097.

III. SIMULATION ASSUMPTIONS

In light of these elements, also given the symmetry and the regular shape of the centerboard over its length, a 2D model has been created with the following cases (Fig.3):

- CASE A. An open trailing edge with a 2 mm edge thickness, corresponding to the centerboard considered a model in reality, where $a_4 = 0.097$;
- CASE B. A closed trailing edge where the Fillet command is applied to reproduce a hand-made sharpening where the $a_4 = 0.097$ and the point is characterized by a 60° inclination in the final part;
- CASE C. A Closed trailing edge with a 45° inclination where again, $a_4 = 0.097$;
- CASE D. A perfectly closed trailing edge where $a_4 = 0.1036$ as a means of control.

The model was defined through a bullet-shaped domain (Fig.3) associated with a characteristic size L of 100 times the chord length, to minimize any boundary effect and keep a reasonably low processing time, where the circular section has a radius of L and the rectangle section has a $2L \times L$ size.

As far as concerns the boundary conditions the free-stream velocity U_{inf} was assumed equal to 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10 m/s, to match the whole speed range of an ILCA class boat (up to 20knts [9]). The simulation is run under the incompressibility assumption given that water is the only flowing substance under a speed of 0.3 Mach [10] and since the Reynolds Number ranges from $3 \cdot 10^5$ to $3 \cdot 10^6$ the turbulent model is described by RANS (Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes) equations [11] and in particular by the SST model, as introduced before.

Fig. 3: Model domain with the airfoil at the center

Along with the U_{inf} parameter, another one is chosen for a sensibility analysis created through the Auxiliary Sweep function: the angle of attack α . This allows studying a broad combination of cases, assuming values for α equal to 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4, where the most probable leeway angle (or drift angle) of the boat is usually supposed to be [12]. The whole model is run under stationary conditions and a temperature of 293.15K and the velocity field is expressed in function of the freestream velocity value and the angle of attack:

$$U_x = U_{inf} \left(\frac{\alpha\pi}{180} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$U_y = U_{inf} \left(\frac{\alpha\pi}{180} \right) \quad (3)$$

Concerning the mesh, a modification is made from the original model and a simpler physics-controlled one is chosen in an attempt to shorten the simulation time from 1 hour to about 30 minutes, accounting for that absolute precision is not mandatory for this study.

IV. RESULTS

a. Drag Force

After the simulation is complete, the program generates by default a 2D plot showing Velocity and Pressure magnitude.

Fig. 2: Case Shapes and relative coefficients

Fig. 4: Velocity magnitude and Pressure contours

In Fig.4 is the case of a 10m/s flow and an angle of attack of 2° and it is, of course, a first valuable hint about the dynamics around the airfoil. The lift region, for example, is indeed asymmetric and it explains why a symmetric centerboard is able to generate a force countering the drift when the angle of attack is non-zero. In particular, the flow coming from “below” implies that the drift happens in the same direction, while the lift is generated on the other side due to an acceleration of the fluid that needs to overcome the leading edge. In the same way, Pressure contours highlight the regions of maximum and minimum Pressure (such as the zones of the leading edge right below and above the symmetry axis). Another interesting representation is given by the flow in the vicinity of the tail of the airfoil.

Fig. 5: Velocity magnitude and Pressure contours

In Fig.5 is well shown the wake owed by the tail and the abrupt deceleration of the water right behind the trailing edge. Here is a low-pressure region, where the vortex shedding effect takes place and where a non-negligible amount of the Drag is expected to be generated. In a perfectly sharpened trailing edge, such a region would be expected to be considerably smaller, indeed, as the flow would not separate easily. Moving now the attention to the Drag, we are only in-

terested in the x-axis which represents the direction pointed by the bow of the boat, while the direction of the flow is the real path followed by the boat. In this sense, the only component useful for this case is indeed the x-axis and it is the one opposing the motion of the boat.

Comsol provides a full set of variables of which the one of interest is $-spf.T_stressx$ which represents the total stress exerted on the airfoil by the fluid, accounting for the Pressure and Viscous Stresses in the sole x direction [13]. Of course, the interest is in the +x component only, which needs to be isolated from the total count and integrated to obtain the total Drag Force acting on the airfoil. This result is obtained in Comsol by plotting $-spf.T_stressx \cdot (-spf.T_stressx > 0)$ (in N/m^2). The plot is now showing the regions interested by the Drag Force only, while the empty ones are the regions where a low pressure (thus a lift force pointing up and to the left) manifests. The next step is a line integration interesting all the boundaries of the airfoil and generating a table with all the combinations for the selected parameters of the sensibility analysis (U_{inf} and α). Repeating the same operation for all the cases four datasets are generated and ready for a mutual comparison. Each dataset is reorganized to obtain clusters of Drag values coupling all the angles of attack for each value of U_{inf} . Due to the large volume of data, in Fig.6 is reported an example showing the lowest speed accounted for the simulation.

Providing that the variations do not change considerably even for the other cases, the difference between an ideally closed trailing edge with respect to the open one is clear. Unfortunately, such modification is difficult to obtain simply by hand, and Case B (Closed Trailing Edge) is the most common result when a sailor attempts to work on his own.

The same case as above can be well visualized in Fig.7 and Fig.8, showing that there is no discernible difference between Cases A, B and C, while Case D is instead well desirable as it brings a decrease in the drag force in the order of 7-13%, depending on the angle of attack. Among all the cases, the minimum decrease between Case A and Case D is obtained for $U_{inf} = 10\text{ m/s}$ and $\alpha = 4^\circ$ and is equal to 5%. The maximum decrease is instead obtained for $U_{inf} = 3\text{m/s}$ and $\alpha = 0^\circ$ and is equal to 13.4%.

b. Drag Coefficient

To complete the analysis more thoroughly and provide more insights for the reader, a full set of Drag Coefficient values has been calculated from the Drag Force, accounting for the

U _{inf} (m/s)	alpha (deg)	Open Trailing Edge	Closed Trailing Edge	Closed 45deg Trailing Edge	Perfect Trailing Edge
		Drag (N/m)	Drag (N/m)	Drag (N/m)	Drag (N/m)
1	0	4.92	4.95	4.94	4.28
1	1	5.09	5.11	5.10	4.51
1	2	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.01
1	3	6.04	6.04	6.05	5.55
1	4	6.41	6.41	6.40	5.96

Incr Drag % Open-Closed	Incr Drag % Open-45	Incr Drag % Open-Perfect
0.56	0.36	-12.98
0.40	0.25	-11.48
0.05	0.01	-9.25
-0.04	0.10	-8.17
0.05	-0.09	-6.99

Fig. 6: Drag Force and Percentual variations for the $U_{inf} = 1$ m/s case

Fig. 7: Plot $U_{inf} = 1$ m/s case

Fig. 8: Plot $U_{inf} = 10$ m/s case

chord as reference length (see last page) [13].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work a simulation was run with a fine mesh, managing to obtain a processing time in the order of 30 minutes. This allowed indeed to save much time and repeat the simulation being free to verify several changes and attempts. Providing that the whole model is executed on a Lenovo IdeaPad 310 enhanced by an SSD, the result can be considered sufficient. Given the results reported in the previous paragraph, the idea of sharpening the trailing edge appears to be legitimate when it comes to creating a tail of zero thickness. In reality, this result is hard to obtain by hand and the real case (Case B or C) would produce a negative or no effect at all in decreasing the total drag on the centerboard. The negative effect of bad sharpening can be explained by the length of the trailing edge region interested in this modification. The region is indeed so small (1-2mm respect a 370mm chord) that the flow “sees” it as a rounded trailing edge. In this sense, the NASA Technical Memorandum TM-X-3060 [14] shows plenty of data about the increase of the Drag Coefficient owed to a rounded trailing edge in a NACA 0012 airfoil at high Reynolds numbers.

Moreover, the values of the Drag Coefficient obtained from this work are in line with the results from another work made by Hu et.al. in very similar conditions [15]. A final remark is about the angle of attack. It is clear that a value close to zero will be typical of a downwind course, while a value of 3-4 ° will be more characteristic of a close-hauled course.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The Centerboard used for the study is provided by an ILCA boat produced by Performance Sailcraft Australia (PSA). The Author wants to highlight that PSA was not involved nor requested of funded the study in any way.

REFERENCES

- [1] International Laser Class Association. [Online] 2022. <http://www.laserinternational.org/>.
- [2] *Flow Around an Inclined NACA 0012 Airfoil*. Comsol Inc. Application ID: 14629.
- [3] Menter, F.R. *Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications* NASA Antes Research Center. Moffet Field : s.n., 1994. AIAA Journal - Vol. 32, No. 8.
- [4] LADSON, Charles L. *Effects of independent variation of Mach and Reynolds numbers on the low-speed aerodynamic characteristics of the NACA 0012 airfoil section*. Scientific and Technical Information Division, NASA Langley Research Center. 1988. NASA Technical Memorandum 4074.
- [5] Gregory, Nigel, and C. L. O'reilly. *Low-speed aerodynamic characteristics of NACA 0012 aerofoil section, including the effects of upper-surface roughness simulating hoar frost*. Aerodynamics Division, N.P.L., British Ministry of Defence. 1970. Reports and Memoranda No. 3726 .
- [6] Jacobs, Eastman N., Ward, Kenneth E. and Pinkerton, Robert M. *The characteristics of 78 related airfoil sections from tests in the variable-density wind tunnel*. National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics. 1933. NACA-TR-460. Document ID 19930091108.
- [7] ILCA Class Rules. International Laser Class Association (ILCA). 2020.
- [8] Rumsey, Christopher. *Turbulence Modeling Resource*. NASA Langley Research Center. 2022.
- [9] *Australian Speed Rivalry*. ILCA website. [Online] 2020. <http://www.laserinternational.org/blog/2020/12/04/australian-speed-rivalry/>.
- [10] Mattioli, Ennio. *Aerodinamica*. s.l. : Levrotto Bella; 3^o edizione, 1992. p. 600. ISBN-10: 8882180298.
- [11] Osborne, Reynolds. IV. *On the dynamical theory of incompressible viscous fluids and the determination of the criterion*. Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. 1895. (A.)186123–164.
- [12] *Experimental investigation of the wave pattern around a sailing yacht model*. SFAKIANAKI, K., LIAROKAPIS, D. and TZABIRAS, G. D. s.l. : Rizzuto Guedes Soares (eds), 2012, Sustainable Maritime Transportation and Exploitation of Sea Resources. ISBN 978-0-415-62081-9.
- [13] Lyu, Peter. *How Do I Compute Lift and Drag?* Comsol Blog. [Online] 2015. <https://www.comsol.de/blogs/how-do-i-compute-lift-and-drag/>.
- [14] Beasley, William D. and McGhee, Robert J. *Low-speed aerodynamic characteristics of airfoil sections with rounded trailing edges in forward and reverse flow*. NASA Langley research Center. 1974. NASA-TM-X-3060 . Document ID: 19740025317.
- [15] *Numerical simulation on vortex shedding from a hydrofoil in steady flow*. Jian Hu, Zibin Wang, Wang Zhao, Shili Sun, Cong Sun and Chunyu Guo. s.l. : MDPI, 2020, p. 8.3: 195. Journal of Marine Science and Engineering.

U _{inf}	alpha	Drag Coefficient			
		Open (Case A)	Closed (Case B)	Closed 45° (Case C)	Perfect (Case D)
1	0	0.0266	0.0268	0.0267	0.0232
1	1	0.0276	0.0277	0.0276	0.0244
1	2	0.0299	0.0299	0.0299	0.0271
1	3	0.0327	0.0327	0.0328	0.0300
1	4	0.0347	0.0347	0.0347	0.0323
3	0	0.0246	0.0247	0.0246	0.0213
3	1	0.0255	0.0256	0.0256	0.0225
3	2	0.0276	0.0277	0.0277	0.0250
3	3	0.0305	0.0304	0.0305	0.0281
3	4	0.0326	0.0326	0.0326	0.0305
5	0	0.0233	0.0234	0.0233	0.0202
5	1	0.0242	0.0243	0.0242	0.0214
5	2	0.0262	0.0263	0.0263	0.0237
5	3	0.0289	0.0289	0.0290	0.0268
5	4	0.0311	0.0311	0.0311	0.0293
7	0	0.0225	0.0226	0.0225	0.0196
7	1	0.0233	0.0235	0.0234	0.0207
7	2	0.0253	0.0254	0.0253	0.0230
7	3	0.0280	0.0279	0.0280	0.0260
7	4	0.0302	0.0302	0.0301	0.0286
10	0	0.0217	0.0219	0.0218	0.0190
10	1	0.0226	0.0227	0.0227	0.0202
10	2	0.0245	0.0246	0.0246	0.0224
10	3	0.0271	0.0271	0.0271	0.0253
10	4	0.0295	0.0293	0.0293	0.0280

Fig. 9: Full Set of Drag Coefficients for all the presented cases